

A New Flavonoltetraglycoside from Guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) Leaves

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In continuation of our work^{1,2} on Guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L. Taub.), we report herein the isolation of a new flavonol tetraglycoside from this plant.

Sample (1 kg) of dried powdered leaves was refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°; 5 dm³) for 6 h. It was followed by extractions with 80% aqueous methanol (4×4 dm³) under reflux for 6 h each time. The pooled methanolic extracts was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure.

Paper chromatography (including 2-D) was done using solvent system butan-1-ol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5, v/v/v), aqueous acetic acid (2.2%, v/v). The various detecting reagents used were (i) FeCl₃-K₃Fe(CN)₆³ : phenolic compounds, (ii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) AlCl₃⁴ : flavonols, (iii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) FeCl₃⁵ : di-OH-phenolics, (iv) sodium-metaperiodate benzidine reagent⁶ : phenolic glycosides, and (v) aniline hydrogenphthalate⁷ : reducing sugars.

Acid hydrolysis of flavonolglycoside (Found : C, 51.79 ; H, 5.46. C₃₉H₆₀O₂₄ requires : C, 51.88 ; H, 5.54%) was carried out in 95% ethanol-2M HCl (1 : 1) at 100° for 1 h. Aglycones were detected under uv-light, whereas sugars were identified by spraying with anilinehydrogenphthalate reagent⁷. Partial hydrolysis was carried out in 1M HCl for 40 min at 100° and the method of Harborne⁸ was employed for the quantitative estimation of aglycones and sugars.

On hydrolysis⁹ with acid, the flavonolglycoside yielded kaempferol, L-rhamnose and D-glucose. The nature of uv peaks at 265, 346 and 402 nm in the presence of NaOAc, NaOMe and AlCl₃, was in agreement with those of kaempferol-3, 7-O-diglucoside or kaempferol-3-O-rhamnoside-7-O-glucoside ; thus indicating the absence of free phenolic group at C-3 and C-7. Flavonolglycoside

was acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine, at room temperature. The ¹H nmr (90 MHz ; CCl₄) spectrum of the acetylated derivatives showed signals at δ 1.85–2.25 (42H, s, 14×acetate-CH₃), 0.93 and 1.33 (6H, unresolved d, 2×rhamnose-CH₃), 3.40 (2H, s, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), 3.60–4.01 (2H, unresolved quartet, rhamnose-C-5-H), 4.85–5.50 (20H, m, primary and secondary-H of glucose/rhamnose), doublet and multiplet at 6.65 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar 6-H), 6.95 (1H, J 3 Hz, Ar 8-H) and 7.35–7.85 (4H, Ar-2',3',5',6'-H). The glycosylation of 7-hydroxyl group was supported by downfield shift¹⁰ in pmr spectra (indicated by signals at δ 6.65 (d, 6-H), 6.95 (d, 8-H). Moreover, in ¹H nmr (90 MHz ; CDCl₃) spectra of silylated flavonolglycoside, the sugar region showed signals at δ 1.04 and 1.25 (6H, d, J 6.5 Hz each, 2×rhamnose-CH₃), 4.25 and 5.20 (2H, m, rhamnose/glucose-C-1-H), 3.1–4.0 (20H, m, primary and secondary-H of glucose/rhamnose) and unresolved doublets and doublets at 6.15, 6.65, 7.15 and 7.85 (2H each, J 9.0 Hz each, Ar-2',3',5',6',6,8-H).

Mass spectral fragments¹¹ m/z 450, 362 (terminal glucose, rhamnose), 378, 289 (internal glucose, rhamnose), 414 ((aglycone + H) – 15) and 740, 650 (1→2 interglycosidic linkage) and ¹H nmr spectra (TMS ether)⁹ of flavonolglycoside and its acetyl derivative confirmed that the parent glycoside contained two rhamnose, two glucose units ; m/z (rel. int.%), 740 (0.6), 650 (0.5), 635 (0.5), 585 (0.6), 450 (2.5), 430 (1.0), 414 (4.5), 378 (1.5), 362 (1.61), 361 (2.42), 331 (2.0), 319 (4.03), 305 (6.45), 289 (11.29), 259 (5.65), 243 (6.45), 231 (4.84), 230 (3.22), 218 (14.52), 217 (62.9), 199 (4.84), 191 (15.32), 189 (6.45), 169 (8.06), 159 (6.45), 157 (7.26), 149 (16.13), 148 (10.48), 147 (58.87), 145 (5.64), 143 (4.84), 134 (3.22), 133 (19.35), 131 (11.29), 130 (4.84), 129 (31.45), 119 (7.26), 117 (15.32), 116 (5.64), 103

(28.22), 101 (3.22), 89 (3.22), 75 (12.90), 74 (8.87) and 73 (100).

The position of the glucosidic and 3-O-(2-glucosyl-dirhamnosyl) or glucosidic and 3-O-(2-dirhamnosylglucosyl) was determined by enzymatic hydrolysis⁹ of flavonoltetraglycoside with β -glucosidase, which supported latter, i.e. 3-O-(2-dirhamnosylglucosyl)-7-O- β -glucosylkaempferol; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 720, 1 050 (OCOCH₃), 1 620, 1 435, 1 375 (C=C), 1 755, 1 110, 1070 (C=CO) and 2 960 cm⁻¹ (CH); λ_{\max} (methanol) 246sh, 262, 318sh, 346; (+NaOCH₃) 248, 266, 301, 346, 392; (+AlCl₃) 260sh, 272, 301, 345, 402; (+AlCl₃-HCl) 276, 296sh, 345, 400; (+CH₃COONa) 265, 320sh, 354, 410 and (+CH₃COONa + H₃BO₃) 254, 322sh, 349; λ_{\max} (hydrolysed, methanol) 264sh, 293sh, 321sh, 365; (+NaOCH₃) 275, 316, 416; (+AlCl₃) 261sh, 268, 366, 428; (+AlCl₃-HCl), 260, 270, 365, 426; (+CH₃COONa) 272, 302, 385 nm.

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